

Public Relations Strategies and Their Effectiveness in Conflict Resolution: a Study of Akwa Ibom State University

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Abstract

This study examines the public relations strategies employed by Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU), Obio Akpa Campus, and evaluates their effectiveness in resolving conflicts related to the non-employment of host community indigenes. Guided by stakeholder theory and social responsibility theory, the study adopts a mixed-methods design, integrating surveys and in-depth interviews. A sample of 322 respondents from the Obio Akpa community was drawn using Philip Meyer's sampling formula. Data were analysed through descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. Findings revealed that the university employs dialogue, community engagement, outreach programmes, and stakeholder consultations to manage conflicts. While these strategies have helped ease tensions, they have not fully met community expectations regarding equitable employment. Challenges identified include lack of transparency in employment communication, weak follow-ups on community outreach promises and bureaucratic delays in governance handling. The study recommends participatory communication, policy alignment with local needs, and a shift towards a two-way symmetrical communication model for sustainable conflict resolution.

Keywords: Public relations, conflict resolution, stakeholder theory, community engagement, Akwa Ibom State University

1.1 Introduction

Public relations (PR) has evolved from a peripheral communication activity to a strategic management function that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organizations and their publics (Cutlip, Center, & Broom, 2019). Within academic

institutions, public relations functions as the communication bridge that fosters peace, legitimacy, and mutual trust between the university and its host community (Grunig & Hunt, 1984).

In Nigeria, university–community conflicts often emerge from perceived exclusion, inequitable employment, and environmental or social neglect (Ekanem & Eyo, 2018). Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU), located at Obio Akpa in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, has faced periodic friction with its host community over employment opportunities, especially within the security department. This study therefore focuses on examining how AKSU's PR department has managed these tensions through strategic communication and community engagement.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The relationship between universities and their host communities in Nigeria has historically been complex, reflecting broader tensions between institutions and the societies that sustain them. Universities are expected to contribute positively to their immediate environments through employment, social responsibility projects, and community engagement. However, when these expectations are not met or poorly communicated, conflicts often emerge, eroding trust and impeding institutional growth (Fatile & Adejuwon, 2011; Adewale & Afolabi, 2020). This study examined the extent to which the eroded community trust in Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, has escalated due to ineffective public relations strategies, stemming from the non-employment of indigenes in the security department.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study sets out to:

- 1 To identify the PR strategies used by the Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, in resolving host community conflicts.
- 2 To assess the extent to which these PR strategies have been effective in resolving conflicts between the university and the host community over the unemployment issue.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026
ISSN: 3026-9733

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2.1 Theoretical Framework

This research was hinged on two theories – stakeholder theory and social responsibility theory.

Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984) argues that organizations must balance the interests of all parties affected by their actions. Host communities, as critical stakeholders, influence an institution's legitimacy and operational peace. A neglect of such stakeholders often results in mistrust and conflict, which can undermine the organization's reputation and lead to operational disruptions.

Social Responsibility Theory (Wright, 1976) posits that institutions have moral obligations to act in the public interest, especially through transparency, accountability, and community engagement. In the context of universities, this theory justifies policies that ensure social inclusion and equitable benefits to host communities.

2.2 Literature Review

2.2.1 Public Relations

Public relations (PR) has evolved significantly from its early twentieth-century roots in publicity and media relations to become a strategic management discipline concerned with building and sustaining relationships between organizations and their publics. According to the Public Relations Society of America (PRSA, 2020, para. 1), PR is “a strategic communication process that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organisations and their publics”. The Chartered Institute of Public Relations (CIPR, 2021) similarly defines PR as a discipline that manages reputation, aiming to build understanding and support while influencing opinions and behaviours.

As the discipline has matured, scholars have increasingly framed PR within the context of stakeholder relations, organisational legitimacy and ethical accountability (Ihlen & van Ruler, 2019). Lattimore et al. (2021) argue that PR functions as a bridge between an organization and its environment, scanning social and political trends, advising management on stakeholder concerns, and facilitating communication that aligns institutional policies with public expectations. This reflects the transition of PR from reactive publicity to proactive strategic communication.

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Moreover, PR has been conceptualised as a constitutive practice as organisations engage in communication not merely to transmit messages but to negotiate meaning, build trust and manage reputational assets (Fawkes, 2022). In this sense, PR is inherently relational and embedded in organizational governance rather than being a peripheral function. Consequently, its role in conflict prevention, stakeholder engagement and institutional legitimacy is increasingly acknowledged (Olayinka & Olufemi, 2021).

2.2.2 Conflict and Conflict Resolution

Conflict constitutes a pervasive feature of human societies and organisations. It is typically defined as a process in which one party perceives that another party has negatively affected, or is about to negatively affect, something that the first party cares about (Rahim, 2017). Conflict may manifest in various forms (interpersonal, intra-group, inter-group, organisational, or community) and often arises from incompatible goals, scarce resources, communication breakdowns, or perceived injustice (Deutsch, 2019; Omosire & Abiodun, 2014).

The literature distinguishes between destructive and constructive conflict. While destructive conflict undermines cooperation and organisational performance, constructive conflict (when properly managed) can stimulate innovation, clarify issues, and improve decision-making (Albert, 2011). The key distinction lies in the management process, as conflict itself is not inherently harmful but becomes problematic when poorly managed.

Conflict resolution involves the systematic transformation of conflictual relationships through communication, negotiation, problem-solving, and structural change (Lederach, 2017). It is concerned not only with settling disputes but also with addressing root causes and rebuilding relationships. Ramsbotham, Woodhouse, and Miall (2016) highlight the importance of inclusive dialogue, power-sharing, and institutional reforms as integral to sustainable conflict resolution. In organisational settings, mechanisms such as mediation, arbitration, grievance procedures, and dialogue platforms are often employed to manage conflict (Albert, 2011).

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In higher education and institutional environments, escalating conflict may stem from misalignment between organisational practices and stakeholder expectations, leading to deficits in institutional legitimacy. Consequently, public relations (PR) in such contexts is increasingly recognised as crucial for facilitating conflict resolution through dialogue, transparency, and stakeholder engagement (Ekanem & Akpan, 2021).

2.2.3 Public Relations in Universities and Community Relations

Public relations is defined as a strategic communication process that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organisations and their publics (Cutlip et al., 2019). Beyond image management, PR plays a crucial role in conflict prevention and resolution through communication planning, trust-building, and stakeholder participation (Nwosu, 2017).

Universities worldwide engage in community relations as part of corporate social responsibility (CSR). Aina (2020) asserts that community relations programmes enhance institutional image and promote local development. Nigerian universities, however, often struggle with effective engagement due to bureaucratic inertia, political interference, and inadequate PR structures (Akpan & Ukpong, 2022). Such inertia and neglect frequently breed conflict or escalate tensions into crisis situations.

2.2.4 Conflict and Communication Strategies

Conflict often arises when expectations differ between institutions and their publics. The two-way symmetrical model proposed by James E. Grunig and Todd Hunt (1984) emphasises dialogue, negotiation, and mutual understanding as key mechanisms for resolving such conflicts. Studies show that when universities adopt participatory PR models, emphasising feedback and inclusion, conflicts diminish significantly (Obi, 2021; Nwosu, 2017).

Communities frequently expect employment opportunities, infrastructural development, and social recognition from universities located within their territories. When these expectations remain unmet, resentment and protests may follow (Ekanem & Eyo, 2018). In such circumstances, the mediating function of PR becomes vital in translating institutional policies into community understanding.

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2.2.5 Conflict Resolution and Management

Not all crises are entirely unexpected. A study by the Institute for Crisis Management found that only 14 percent of business crises were unexpected, while the remaining 86 percent were described as “smouldering crises.” This implies that organisations were aware of potential problems long before the public became aware of them. Many smouldering crises can be prevented through effective environmental scanning and issues management, which facilitate the development of strategic plans for handling crises.

Although executives often acknowledge that business crises are almost inevitable, surveys show that approximately 50 percent of companies lack a crisis management plan. While every crisis differs in nature, having a structured plan makes crisis handling significantly easier. Adjusting an existing plan to suit specific situations is far more efficient than starting from scratch when a crisis occurs.

Conflict management as a concept has traditionally been associated with conflict containment and settlement. It refers to the practice of identifying and handling conflict in a sensible, fair, and efficient manner. This process requires skills such as effective communication, problem-solving, and negotiation, with emphasis on addressing underlying interests (Gordon, 2004). According to Robbins and Sanghi (2010), conflict management involves the use of resolution and stimulation techniques to achieve the desired level of conflict within an organisation.

Conflict management aims to enhance learning and group outcomes, thereby improving organisational effectiveness and performance (Rahim, 2002). Importantly, a distinction exists between conflict management and conflict resolution, which extends beyond mere semantics (Robbins, 2005). Conflict management does not necessarily imply the complete elimination of conflict.

According to Robbins (2005), conflict emerges when one party perceives that another party has adversely affected, or is about to adversely affect, something the first party values. Similarly, Mullins and Christy (2013) describe conflict as behaviour intended to obstruct the achievement of another person's goals. These perspectives align with Sims's (2002) assertion that organisational conflicts often arise from incompatible goals or disagreements among individuals and groups.

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Within organisations, conflict may manifest as either functional or dysfunctional conflict. Functional conflict within a group or team can stimulate creativity, innovation, and team development. The emergence of such conflict encourages constructive criticism, suggestions, and healthy competition, ultimately improving group productivity and performance (Wobodo, 2019). This is often facilitated by diversity of opinions, which helps teams identify new ways of solving problems and addressing organisational challenges (Lepsinger, 2018).

3.1 Methodology

The study employed a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques. The population consisted of members of the Obio Akpa host community. Based on the 2006 National Population Census, projected to 2025, the community's total population was 2,640 residents. A sample of 322 respondents was drawn using Philip Meyer's sampling approach. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and in-depth interviews with community leaders and university officials. The data analysis plan involved both quantitative and qualitative techniques, consistent with the mixed-methods design. Quantitative data were coded and analysed using descriptive statistics – frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations – to summarise demographic and substantive responses. The chi-square test of independence was used to test hypotheses and establish associations among variables.

Qualitative data from interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed thematically following the procedures of Braun and Clarke (2019). Themes were derived through explanation building to interpret patterns of meaning relating to AKSU's public relations strategies and conflict management practices. Findings from both approaches were integrated during interpretation to provide a unified understanding of the research questions.

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4.1 Findings

Table 1: PR Strategies used by AKSU in Conflict Resolution

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total Score	N	3.0 WMS	Decision Rule
1	AKSU uses dialogue and negotiation as PR strategies to resolve conflicts with the host community	90	164	40	28	960	322	3.0	Positive/ Accepted
2	Public meetings and town hall sessions are regularly organised to address issues related to employment	72	157	59	34	911	322	2.82	Negative/ Rejected
3	Management of AKSU communicates openly and promptly during crises	57	97	128	40	815	322	2.53	Negative/ Rejected
4	The University uses community outreach programmes to build positive relationships	76	167	49	30	933	322	2.89	Negative/ Rejected
5	AKSU engages local media and traditional rulers as part of conflict resolution strategy	72	158	60	32	914	322	2.83	Negative/ Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2025

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Statement 1 in Table 1 above reveals with a WMS of 3.0 that respondents believe the university uses dialogue and negotiation in resolving conflicts. The positive responses suggest that the university recognises the importance of inclusive communication and attempts to engage stakeholders constructively.

Statement 2 revealed with a WMS of 2.82 that the university does not organise town hall meetings and public sessions to discuss employment issues with the host community. This indicates a moderately negative perception of participatory engagement. The significant level of disagreement suggests that such meetings do not exist or are not inclusive enough, potentially fuelling misunderstandings and employment-related conflicts.

Statement 3 shows with a WMS of 2.53 that respondents disagree that the university communicates openly during crises. This result points to a communication gap during conflict situations. Given that employment-related disputes are highly sensitive, a lack of timely and transparent communication may lead to heightened tensions and distrust between the university and the host community. Strengthening real-time information channels could improve stakeholder confidence.

Statement 4 revealed with a WMS of 2.89 that the university does not conduct community outreach programmes to foster positive relations. This demonstrates that the institution does not recognise community engagement as a PR strategy. This indicates that outreach efforts may not reach all segments of the community, suggesting a need for broader inclusion, particularly involving unemployed indigenes who are central to the employment-related conflicts.

Statement 5 reveals with a WMS of 2.83 that the university does not involve local media and traditional rulers in resolving conflicts. This finding underscores the institution's non-recognition of cultural leadership structures and the role of mass communication in de-escalating disputes. This suggests that some stakeholders may feel excluded from these processes, highlighting a need for wider consultations with community representatives.

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Table 2 Extent to which the PR Strategies adopted by the University have reduced tension between the host community and the institution.

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total Score	N	3.0 WMS	Decision Rule
1	The PR strategies adopted by the University have reduced tensions between the host community and the institution.	69	157	60	36	903	322	2.80	Negative/ Rejected
2	Conflicts arising from the non-employment of indigenes have been effectively addressed by the university	53	140	68	51	819	322	2.54	Negative/ Rejected
3	The University's PR strategies promote peaceful co-existence with the host community	68	180	44	30	930	322	2.88	Negative/ Rejected
4	Conflicts related to employment significantly in recent years	57	154	62	49	863	322	2.68	Negative/ Rejected
5	The host community trusts the university's conflict resolution approaches	53	158	66	44	862	322	2.67	Negative/ Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 (Statement 1) shows with a WMS of 2.80 that the university's PR strategies have not reduced tensions between the institution and the host community. This result indicates that there are lingering perceptions of unresolved grievances. This implies the university's efforts may not yet have fully addressed employment-related disputes, particularly concerning security recruitment.

Table 2 (Statement 2) reveals with a WMS of 2.54 the university has not effectively resolved conflicts stemming from the non-employment of indigenes. This demonstrates that the non-inclusion of Obio Akpa indigenes in the security department remains a contentious issue, suggesting that existing PR strategies may lack direct responses to community employment demands. A more inclusive employment policy could significantly enhance conflict resolution outcomes.

Table 2 (statement 3) illustrates with a WMS of 2.88 that the university's PR strategies do not contribute to peaceful coexistence with the host community. This highlights that, despite the PR-driven engagement mechanism, the overall relationship remains unstable due to some outstanding employment-related groups.

Table 2 (Statement 4) reveals with a WMS of 2.68 that employment-related conflicts have not decreased in recent years. This finding suggests that the non-employment of Obio Akpa indigenes continues to fuel disputes.

Table 2 (Statement 5) revealed, with a WMS of 2.67, respondents' distrust in the university's conflict resolution processes. This highlights a trust deficit between the university and the host community, likely driven by perceived exclusion in employment decisions.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

Objective One: To identify the PR strategies used by Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, in resolving host community conflicts.

There are various PR strategies used by Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, to resolve conflicts arising from the non-employment of Obio Akpa indigenes in the Security Department. The university uses dialogue and negotiation as PR strategies to resolve conflicts, with a WMS of 3.0 (Table 1 Statement 1). In contradiction, the university does not regularly organise public meetings and town hall sessions to address issues related to employment, as shown in Table 1 (Statement 2),

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with a WMS of 2.82. Furthermore, community outreach programmes were not a key PR strategy used by the university to build positive relationships with the host community, with a WMS of 2.89 as portrayed in Table 1 (Statement 4).

Furthermore, Table 1 (Statement 3) revealed with a WMS of 2.53 that management of AKSU does not communicate openly and promptly during crises. The university does not involve local media and traditional rulers as part of its conflict resolution process. From Table 1 with a WMS of 2.83 (Statement 5). These findings indicate that the university only relies on dialogue and negotiation to manage conflicts effectively.

On the public relations strategies adopted by AKSU to address conflicts arising from the non-employment of Obio Akpa indigenes in the security department, the head of the PR/Information unit mentioned the use of dialogue, negotiation and town hall meetings. This view was corroborated by the HOC, Obio Akpa Campus, who said that currently indigenes of the Obio Akpa community are the ones employed to work in the security department of AKSU. In a similar view, the CLO agreed to the use of dialogue, negotiation and employment of indigenes to serve in the security department of AKSU.

The findings suggest that the university prioritises communication-based PR strategies to foster mutual understanding and reduce tensions with the host community. The irregular use of town hall meetings, traditional leadership involvement, and partnerships with local media highlights the institution's awareness of the socio-cultural dynamics of the Obio Akpa community. However, the existence of neutral and dissenting views points to lingering gaps in trust and satisfaction, implying that these strategies may not fully meet community expectations. These findings align with the study by Okoro and Agbo (2020), which established that dialogue and stakeholder engagement are vital for managing institutional conflicts in Nigerian universities. Findings of this study contradict Akpan and Effiong (2021), whose study emphasised the role of community outreach programmes and traditional authority involvement in promoting peace between host communities and academic institutions. More so, the results corroborate with Udo and Inyang's (2019) findings, whose research revealed that many universities fail to integrate local media and traditional rulers into their PR strategies, often leading to escalated tensions.

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The findings are further explained by the Excellence Theory of Public Relations (Grunig & Hunt, 1984), which advocates for two-way symmetrical communication between organisations and their publics. By adopting strategies such as dialogue, negotiation, and stakeholder engagement, the university would have demonstrated an intention to create mutual understanding and resolve conflicts amicably.

Objective Two: To assess the extent to which these PR strategies have been effective in resolving conflicts between the university and the host community over the unemployment issue.

The extent to which the PR strategies adopted by Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, have not been effective in addressing conflicts between the university and the host community. Findings in Table 2 (Statement 1) indicate that the PR strategies adopted by the university have not reduced tension between the host community and the institution. However, the findings from Table 2 (Statement 2) revealed a different perspective when looking at employment-related conflicts specifically. Conflicts arising from the non-employment of indigenes have not been effectively addressed, as shown with a WMS of 2.54. This shows that the university's PR strategies have been less effective in resolving employment-specific disputes.

From table 2 (Statement 3), the university's PR strategies do not promote peaceful co-existence with the host community. This is evident given the WMS of 2.88. Similarly, Table 2 (Statement 4) revealed that conflicts related to employment have not decreased in recent years. This is portrayed with a WMS of 2.68.

Furthermore, from table 2 (Statement 5), the host community does not trust the university's conflict resolution approaches. This is evident with a WMS of 2.67. Furthermore, Table 2 revealed a relationship between PR strategies adopted by AKSU and effective conflict resolution.

Concerning the extent to which the PR strategies have been effective in addressing conflicts between the university and the host community over non-employment of indigenes, the Head of the PR/Information unit, Head of Campus, and Community Liaison Officer all agreed that the strategies employed are very effective. According to the HOC, this is evident in the harmonious relationship currently in existence since the employment of indigenes in the security department.

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These findings suggest that the university's initiative of dialogue has played a significant role in reducing tensions and enhancing mutual understanding, but it falls short of addressing the core grievance regarding the non-employment of Obio Akpa indigenes in the security department. The strategies appear more effective in promoting positive perceptions and harmonious coexistence than in delivering tangible employment outcomes. The results align with Okafor and Umeh (2020), who found that Nigerian universities frequently adopt communication-focused PR strategies that enhance community relations but often fail to resolve underlying structural issues, such as employment grievances. Similarly, Etuk and Ekanem (2021) observed that while outreach programmes improve institutional reputation, they have limited impact when communities do not see direct socio-economic benefits. The persistence of grievances among the Obio Akpa community suggests that engagement without actionable outcomes remains insufficient.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings can be explained using the Excellence Theory of Public Relations (Grunig & Hunt, 1984), which emphasises two-way symmetrical communication for effective conflict resolution. While the university engages in dialogue, the limited success in addressing employment-related issues indicates that the process may not be fully mutual. The findings show that AKSU employs traditional PR mechanisms such as dialogue, public meetings, and community relations programmes, to ease host community tensions. However, these strategies often lack follow-up actions that reflect community needs. This supports the assertion by Grunig and Hunt (1984) that asymmetrical communication models often fail in the long term because they prioritise organisational image over relationship-building.

The low trust levels reported in interviews further confirm Nwosu's (2017) argument that weak institutional communication structures undermine stakeholder confidence. True effectiveness, therefore, depends on two-way communication that integrates community input into policy outcomes.

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5.1 Conclusion

AKSU's PR strategies have contributed to peacebuilding and mutual tolerance with the host community but remain insufficient in addressing core employment grievances. The absence of consistent feedback mechanisms and participatory engagement has limited the long-term impact of the PR initiatives.

5.2 Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of PR strategies, the university should conduct periodic assessments, implement follow-up meetings, establish conflict monitoring committees, and provide transparent reporting on actions taken to address co

To strengthen conflict management and improve relations between Akwa Ibom State University and its host communities, several strategic measures are recommended. First, the university should institutionalise participatory communication frameworks that allow community representatives to be actively involved in decision-making processes. Such inclusive structures ensure that issues affecting the community are addressed collaboratively, reducing misunderstanding and fostering mutual respect.

Finally, it is important for the institution to align its recruitment policies with the expectations of the host community. By promoting fairness, transparency, and equitable access to employment opportunities, the university can enhance local goodwill and reduce grievances related to perceived marginalisation.

In addition, the adoption of a two-way symmetrical public relations model is essential. This approach encourages genuine dialogue, openness, and the exchange of feedback between the university and community members, thereby reinforcing trust and improving long-term cooperation.

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